

Sustainability challenges in the bovine sector and the implementation of waste management policies within the EU framework

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ABSTRACT

Globally, the agri-food chain produces nearly 1.3 billion tonnes of waste each year, with the bovine sector being a major contributor. As meat production has soared by more than 40% since 2000, and animal products now provide around 40% of the world's protein, livestock stands as both a cornerstone of global nutrition and a source of pressing environmental challenges. While existing EU waste policies often focus on volume reduction, a transition toward circular and sustainable waste management is essential to ensure long-term sectoral resilience. The Circular Economy Action Plan, a cornerstone of the European Union's Green Deal, provides a framework for advancing sustainability and resource efficiency. Within this context, integrating advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), precision farming, and real-time data analytics offer pathways to reduce waste and improve resource efficiency. Their effective use, however, relies on interdisciplinary collaboration to improve efficiency, minimize waste, and strengthen productivity across the bovine supply chain. This report examines current gaps in both policy and practice within the bovine sector, highlights innovative smart farming solutions, and anticipates emerging sustainability challenges. It further identifies practical opportunities for enhancing circularity and resource efficiency, with implications exceeding beyond the bovine industry to the broader agri-food system.

1. Introduction

Environmental challenges present significant threats to the long-term sustainability of the agricultural sector, with bovine production systems being particularly vulnerable. These systems are resource-intensive and generate considerable environmental impacts, including greenhouse gas emissions, land degradation, and large volumes of organic waste (Zhang et al., 2023). These activities have significantly contributed to rising atmospheric CO₂ levels, intensifying climate-related risks and impacting both ecosystem stability and consumer well-being (Gallo et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2023). In response to these escalating environmental pressures, prioritizing green development has become essential for ensuring the long-term viability of the bovine sector. Green development emphasizes low-carbon practices, resource efficiency, and ecosystem preservation while maintaining productivity, and is increasingly supported by EU and global policies to address climate, health, and food security concerns (Bhat, 2021; FAO, 2013).

Recent estimates by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) reveal that nearly one-third of all food intended for human consumption is lost or wasted annually across the global supply chain (FAO (2013). Food waste undermines food security and places additional pressure on environmental and natural resources. Upcycling food losses and by-products is recognized as an effective strategy to address these global challenges. The EU's Circular Economy Action Plan, central to the Green Deal, promotes waste reduction and sustainability, with the goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050 (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015). Environmental degradation, resource scarcity, and regional disparities are further driven by food waste and excessive plastic use, both of which contribute significantly to ecological harm (Lucifero, 2016; Mielinger & Weinrich, 2023). Livestock production supports global livelihoods but also contributes substantially to greenhouse gas emissions, highlighting the urgent need for more sustainable management practices (FAO, 2013). Despite growing consumer interest in healthier diets, global meat production continues to rise, making sustainable management increasingly critical. Animal products supply approximately 40 % of global

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protein intake, and the surge in meat consumption presents significant waste management challenges for the industry (Kuo et al., 2024). Between 2000 and 2019, global meat production increased by 44 %, reaching 337 million tons. In 2022, production was recorded at 316 million tons, with projections estimating an increase to nearly 374 million tons by 2024 (FAO, 2024, 2023, 2021). Bovine meat production alone accounted for about 65 million tons in 2022, underscoring the sector's continued growth and its dual role as an important economic and nutritional resource on a global scale (FAO, 2024).

In the bovine sector, food loss can occur at multiple stages of the supply chain, from primary production to end consumption. As the industry continues to expand, it generates significant volumes of by-products such as hides, bones, whey, offal, blood, and manure. While often undervalued, these materials represent both a waste management challenge and an opportunity for resource recovery and circular economy practices. These by-products have high valorization potential across industries including pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, dietary supplements, and animal feed manufacturing (Gama Pantoja et al., 2022; Hassoun et al., 2024; Kuo et al., 2024; Lappa et al., 2019). They provide essential nutrients such as proteins, fats, and vitamins A, B6, and B12, along with a wide range of valuable compounds. Hides and bones are rich in collagen and gelatin, which are widely used in medical, cosmetic, and food applications. Bones also supply calcium and phosphorus, making them important for supplements and fertilizers. Whey contains lactic acid and bioactive peptides that play roles in functional foods and antimicrobial agents (Kuo et al., 2024; Lappa et al., 2019). Offal and organs provide enzymes and hormones used in pharmaceuticals, while blood yields hemoglobin and plasma proteins for biofertilizers and specialty biochemical products (Kuo et al., 2024; Mullen & Álvarez, 2016). Notably, bovine feces represent a particularly underexploited yet vital resource with great potential for advancing sustainable waste management practices, including bioenergy production, soil enrichment, and circular nutrient cycles, which refer to the reuse of nutrients within agricultural systems to close material loops and reduce external inputs (de Azevedo et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2024). Through anaerobic digestion, fecal matter can be converted into biogas, offering a renewable energy source, while the resulting digestate serves as a nutrient-dense organic fertilizer (de Azevedo et al., 2017; Tampio et al., 2024). Composting is another viable strategy, improving soil health and contributing to circular nutrient cycles. Effective valorization of bovine by-products not only reduces pollution and greenhouse gas emissions but also contributes to a sustainable bioeconomy by generating value-added products (Gama Pantoja et al., 2022; Hassoun et al., 2024; Kuo et al., 2024; Lappa et al., 2019).

Aligned with the EU's sustainability goals, the valorization of cattle farming by-products is essential for developing a more resilient and efficient agricultural system, as it helps mitigate environmental impacts and promotes the transition to a circular economy through resource recovery and reuse. In the dairy sector specifically, losses frequently result from animal health problems, product spoilage, and the expiration of goods with limited shelf-life, all of which contribute to notable economic inefficiencies and environmental burdens (Lin et al., 2022). In addition to fluid milk losses, significant volumes of by-products such as whey, buttermilk, skim milk, and milk fat residues are often underutilized or discarded (Lappa et al., 2019). When recovered and transformed into high-value ingredients for food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics, and feed, these materials reduce waste and enhance both sustainability and profitability in the dairy sector (Kontogianni et al., 2023; Lappa et al., 2019; León-López et al., 2022; Mehra et al., 2021; Schoina et al., 2020).

In the context of Dairy 4.0, which refers to the application of Industry 4.0 digital technologies in dairy and livestock systems, the integration of advanced digital technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analysis (BDA), and digital twin systems is transforming the bovine and dairy industries (De Vries et al., 2023; Shin et al., 2025). For example, AI-driven optimization and IoT sensors improve the recovery of whey, a major by-product of

cheese production, enabling the extraction of proteins, lactose, and lipids for nutritional, pharmaceutical, and food applications (De Vries et al., 2023; Lappa et al., 2019). IoT-connected equipment ensures continuous quality control, while blockchain enhances traceability and consumer trust (Hawashin et al., 2025). Digital twins simulate and optimize processing operations, reducing waste and improving resource efficiency. Collectively, these technologies advance a circular economy within the bovine and dairy sector, transforming waste streams into valuable resources and aligning with sustainability objectives.

2. Waste reduction policy implications in the bovine sector – EU policy

Effective waste reduction in the bovine sector requires a strong policy foundation, and within the European Union, this foundation is shaped by a range of directives and strategies aimed at minimizing environmental impact while promoting sustainable agricultural practices. Food loss in the bovine sector occurs throughout the supply chain and significantly contributes to resource inefficiency and environmental degradation. To address this, the EU has implemented several regulations and initiatives targeting food loss and waste, while also promoting broader sustainability goals. For example, the Common Market Organization Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013) provides a framework for organizing agricultural markets, including beef, aiming to stabilize markets, ensure fair income for farmers, and enhance agricultural productivity (Shah et al., 2024). It incorporates market monitoring and intervention tools designed to manage supply and minimize waste.

Beyond reducing waste, EU policies increasingly emphasize the recycling and valorization of bovine biomass such as manure, slurry, and processing by-products to decrease dependency on natural resources and enhance circularity among agricultural systems. The repurposing cattle breeding wastes may support multiple environmental benefits, including mitigating greenhouse gas emissions, reducing the competition between feed and food, and alleviating pressure on critical resources such as land and water (Latka et al., 2022). However, transitioning toward circular models introduces complex regional challenges, particularly concerning rural livelihoods and equitable distribution of benefits. In an interconnected food system, such interventions may offer advantages to some stakeholders while imposing new constraints on others, making these issues central to ongoing EU agricultural policy debates.

To support its circular economy and sustainability goals, the European Union has established a comprehensive legal framework to regulate waste generation and management. At the core of this framework is the Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC), which outlines a waste hierarchy that prioritizes prevention, reuse, recycling, and recovery over final disposal (Gharfalkar et al., 2015). Complementing this directive is the Animal By-Products Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009), which provides a detailed system for the safe handling of animal by-products by classifying them based on risk levels and prescribing specific processing and disposal methods appropriate to each category (Bijlsma et al., 2013). Additionally, the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED), enforced in 2010, has been revised to include stricter emission limits for large-scale pig and poultry operations. However, intensive cattle farming remains excluded from the directive, despite its substantial environmental footprint, particularly in terms of methane emissions and nutrient pollution (Romero-Castro et al., 2022). A reassessment of this exclusion is scheduled for 2026, reflecting the EU's the EU's growing intent to include the bovine sector in broader environmental regulations.

Evaluations of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) indicate that its effectiveness in promoting improved manure management has been limited and regionally heterogeneous. The European Court of Auditors reported that the CAP has "rarely incentivized" the uptake of core mitigation measures, such as covered storage, low-emission slurry

spreading, and nutrient management planning, thereby restricting its overall contribution to climate mitigation at the EU level (Nordbeck et al., 2025). These measures have contributed to measurable reductions in ammonia emissions and nitrate leaching, although outcomes remain uneven across Member States due to differences in advisory capacity, infrastructure, and financial support.

Similarly, valorization of bovine manure through anaerobic digestion has delivered measurable outcomes. In 2023, Europe produced about 22 billion cubic metres (≈ 234 TWh) of biogas, supported by roughly 1510 biomethane plants (≈ 1324 within the EU-27), many of which co-digest bovine manure with other feedstocks to generate renewable energy and nutrient-rich digestate (Ankathi et al., 2024; Bakkaloglu et al., 2022). Life cycle assessments consistently show that manure-based anaerobic digestion can achieve greenhouse gas reductions of around 70 % compared with conventional storage systems, primarily through methane capture and energy substitution, provided fugitive emissions and digestate management are effectively controlled (Poeschl et al., 2012; Styles et al., 2018). In addition to reducing emissions, anaerobic digestion contributes to nutrient recycling by returning nitrogen and phosphorus to soils, thus supporting circular nutrient flows (Gislason et al., 2023; van den Oever et al., 2021). However, deployment remains concentrated in regions with strong policy support and infrastructure, highlighting the need for broader enabling conditions.

To strengthen sustainability across economic sectors, the European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan drives a comprehensive shift away from traditional linear production models toward integrated circular systems. These systems are designed to maximize resource efficiency, significantly reduce waste generation, and promote the continuous reuse and reintegration of materials throughout entire value chains (Bhat et al., 2023; Dahunsi, 2025; Rakesh & Mahendran, 2024). In the agricultural sector, this shift is reinforced by the Farm to Fork Strategy, which prioritizes waste reduction throughout the food supply chain Fiala et al. (2024). In the bovine sector, these policies support converting organic waste into resources like biofertilizers, renewable energy, and feed supplements, helping close nutrient loops and improve environmental outcomes. Through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), financial tools such as agri-environmental measures (AEMs) incentivize farmers to adopt better manure management and sustainable practices (Nordbeck et al., 2025). However, despite the comprehensiveness of EU policies supporting sustainable agriculture, significant implementation barriers remain, particularly in rural and livestock-dense regions (Nordbeck et al., 2025). These areas often face limitations in infrastructure, technical expertise, and financial accessibility, which constrain the effective deployment of circular economy practices within the bovine sector. While the EU actively promotes circularity, many cattle-farming regions still lack essential enablers, including localized waste treatment facilities, extension services, and innovation support mechanisms (Röder et al., 2024). Addressing these structural deficiencies is critical to ensure EU sustainability objectives.

To bridge these gaps, the EU-funded *AgriDataValue* project has been launched to enhance smart farming capacities and promote sustainable practices within the agricultural sector (Table 1). The *AgriDataValue*

Table 1

Alignment between EU bovine sector policy and *AgriDataValue* EU funded project (AgriDataValue, 2023).

Policy Objective	EU Policy	AgriDataValue Support
Sustainable livestock production	Farm to Fork, Green Deal	AI-powered monitoring of emissions, feed use, and waste
Waste reduction and circular economy	Circular Economy Action Plan	Valorization of bovine waste, resource optimization
Digital innovation in rural agriculture	Digital Europe Programme, CAP	IoT, drones, satellite data for real-time livestock insights
Empowerment of rural and livestock communities	CAP, Rural Development Programs	Deployment of smart farming pilots, training, and support

project, funded by the European Union, presents a groundbreaking, intelligent multi-technology platform designed to unify real-time data streams from IoT sensors, drones, and satellite imagery.

This integrated system enables comprehensive monitoring and management of key agricultural functions, including livestock health, waste handling, and efficient use of resources, paving the way for more data-driven and sustainable farming practices (2023). Leveraging edge cloud computing, real-time IoT sensors (e.g., neck collars, feeders, emission monitors), and GPS tracking, the platform enables precise monitoring of cattle health, behavior, and calving. It also supports proactive management of farm product quality while helping to minimize emissions and other environmental discharges (AgriDataValue, 2023). By leveraging big data and advanced analytics, the project provides farmers with actionable insights to optimize operations, minimize environmental impacts, and improve economic outcomes. Through pilot programs implemented across several EU countries, *AgriDataValue* demonstrates the practical application of digital technologies in promoting circular economy principles within agricultural production and cattle farming. At the same time, it supports knowledge transfer and infrastructure development, particularly in underserved regions (AgriDataValue, 2023). As a result, *AgriDataValue* ultimately delivers significant benefits to stakeholders by enhancing decision-making, and most importantly fostering sustainable, data-driven practices across the agricultural value chain Table 1.

The EU's policy framework for waste reduction and recycling in the bovine sector demonstrates a strong and growing commitment to environmental sustainability, economic resilience, and the transformation of food systems. The *AgriDataValue* program serves to operationalize these policies by delivering advanced digital tools, integrating real-time data, and enhancing infrastructure in rural areas—thus helping to translate EU goals into actionable practices (Table 1). Together, these efforts support the development of a smart, sustainable, and circular future for livestock farming in Europe. Moreover, large-scale funded programs like *AgriDataValue* play a critical role in advancing the agricultural sector by bridging gaps in knowledge and technology (Arvaniti et al., 2024; Borriello et al., 2025; Hassoun et al., 2024; Terpou et al., 2024). Through a combination of regulatory mechanisms, financial incentives, and stakeholder-driven innovation, the EU aims to cultivate a bovine sector that is not only productive but also resource-efficient, low-impact, and fully aligned with the overarching objectives of the European Green Deal (Olczyk & Kuc-Czarnecka, 2025).

3. Food agroindustrial waste valorization: the case of cattle farming

Global environmental concerns related to food wastage have gained significant attention at both regional and sub-sectoral levels (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015; Latka et al., 2022). These insights are especially valuable for decision-makers dedicated to waste reduction efforts. For example, meat wastage, which has substantial environmental repercussions in terms of land use and carbon emissions, is particularly pronounced in high-income regions where approximately 67 % of meat ends up as waste (FAO, 2013). By highlighting the environmental impact of food waste across regions, products, and supply chain stages, this review offers key insights to guide action and engage stakeholders.

Bioeconomy objectives primarily revolve around the conversion of agro-industrial and forestry biomass, particularly its organic waste, into a diverse array of value-added products. These products encompass biofuels, thermal or electric energy, animal feed, biobased chemicals, biopolymers, soil fertilizers, biosorbents, biopharmaceuticals, and even innovative food items; as depicted in Fig. 1. To recover these valuable high-value products from agro-industrial waste, organic manure is acknowledged as a valuable resource and is integrated into biorefineries. The concept of an organic **waste biorefinery** involves utilizing waste materials as an alternative to dedicated biomass or implementing waste

Fig. 1. Agroindustrial waste management: generating value-added products in regard to a sustainable bioeconomy.

management practices that enhance the extraction of value from organic waste (Tsigkou et al., 2022). The biorefinery concept has garnered substantial interest in recent years, thanks to scientific advancements and applied research technologies that focus on extracting value from agro-industrial waste, particularly waste feedstocks. These developments have further solidified the concept's environmental and economic sustainability aspects (Ganatsios et al., 2017).

Another significant initiative in the context of the circular economy is the utilization of *digestate* as a soil fertilizer. After the biorefinery has successfully produced valuable by-products, the remaining digestate can be further valorized as another source of valuable compounds. This approach has the potential to bring about a transformative shift in Europe's agricultural sector by offering an attractive and sustainable alternative to the conventional use of synthetic fertilizers (Zilio et al., 2023). The widespread use of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers has played a pivotal role enabling higher crop yields and supporting food security. However, it has also introduced significant environmental concerns, including soil degradation, water pollution from nutrient runoff, and increased greenhouse gas emissions, highlighting the urgent need for more sustainable nutrient management strategies (Zilio et al., 2023). On the other hand, the adoption of digestate can contribute to the reduction of synthetic fertilizers, supporting effective soil management and promotion of soil health; key aspects of the EU Soil strategy. Additionally, the use of digestate aligns with the objectives of efficient carbon capture, making it a complementary component to the ongoing development of carbon farming policies (EBA, 2022).

Cattle farming involves the breeding of animals to produce products like meat, milk, and other dairy items for human consumption (Mahmud et al., 2021). Traditional circular cattle farming is characterized by a closed-loop system in which cattle farms produce not only dairy products but also valuable by-products that are reintegrated into the agricultural cycle (Fig. 2). By-product waste from cattle, such as dung, is collected in enclosed containers and used to produce organic fertilizers. These fertilizers are then applied to fields through plowing, supporting the cultivation of cereal and legume crops without the use of synthetic pesticides (Ma et al., 2024; Yemata & Mengistu, 2024). Subsequently, vegetable seeds are sown for consecutive crop cycles, further enhancing soil fertility and resource use efficiency. Crop residues and specific cultivated plants are used as vegetarian livestock feed, which completes

Fig. 2. Traditional circular agricultural practices in cattle farming.

the cycle by supporting animal nutrition without reliance on external feed inputs. This integrated approach reduces waste, lowers environmental impacts, and enhances sustainability across the entire cattle farming system.

4. Integration of cattle farming into a sustainable bioeconomy

The transition toward a sustainable bioeconomy requires the integration of cattle breeding systems into circular value chains that promote environmental, economic, and resource efficiency. As illustrated in Fig. 3, this integration can be achieved through a closed-loop approach involving four interconnected components: cattle breeding, by-product valorization, energy and fertilizer recovery, and the agri-food industry.

In this framework, cattle breeding generates both primary products (e.g., meat and milk) and organic residues, which are then valorized through biorefinery processes such as anaerobic digestion, composting, or thermochemical conversion. These processes produce renewable energy and bio-based fertilizers that can be reintegrated into the agri-food sector, reducing dependence on fossil-based inputs and enhancing soil

Fig. 3. Cattle breeding within a sustainable bioeconomy approach.

fertility. This cyclical system not only mitigates waste and greenhouse gas emissions but also contributes to a more resilient and sustainable agricultural model aligned with bioeconomic principles.

The cattle breeding sector, as one of the most prominent components of the global livestock industry, holds significant potential to contribute to multiple dimensions of sustainable development (Fig. 4). It can play both direct and indirect roles in advancing all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with particularly strong relevance to goals such as SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land) (FAO, 2018). Through sustainable practices, resource-efficient production, and inclusive value chains, the cattle sector can support improved livelihoods, food and nutrition security, environmental stewardship, and socio-economic equity.

4.1. Sustainable approaches to improve milk and meat yield

Substantial advancements have been achieved in enhancing animal growth efficiency, largely driven by the incorporation of nutrient-dense feed components, many of which are also suitable for direct human consumption (Salter, 2017). Currently, there are more than 270 million dairy cattle worldwide, each producing an average of approximately 2600 kg of milk per year. However, it's important to note that only 33 countries have a national average milk yield exceeding 6000 kg per year (FAO, 2018). While these countries represent a relatively small fraction, approximately 13 %, of the global dairy cattle population, they contribute to more than 40 % of the world's total milk production. This strong emphasis on enhancing productivity in the dairy industry to ensure food security raises concerns about other aspects of sustainability.

Precision farming enhancing sustainable agriculture

To meet the demands of precision livestock farming such as growth tracking, identification, and behavior monitoring efficient animal detection methods are crucial, with methods like sensing technologies

and IoT being essential. These sensing systems effectively collect data on animals' physiological conditions, movements, behaviors, and surrounding environmental factors (Yin et al., 2023). These technologies, often referred to as smart farming or precision farming, have begun to see implementation in many European countries, particularly in cattle breeding, resulting in positive impacts on meat and milk yield, as well as quality. However, in practice, the rigorous technological approach aimed at improving production efficiency has not yet gained widespread acceptance, and the practical implementation of technology on farms remains somewhat limited (Lovarelli et al., 2020).

Agro-industrial By-Products as Feed towards sustainable agriculture

Current intensive cattle breeding practices heavily rely on using crops suitable for human consumption as animal feed (Yazid et al., 2021). Cattle breeding is feed-intensive, with around 800 g of feed needed to produce just 100 g of beef. Due to the high cost of conventional feed, there is increasing interest in using lower-value alternatives such as fruit and vegetable waste, and by-products from the brewing, wine, and dairy industries, as well as locally sourced agro-industrial residues. This shift seeks to enhance sustainability and lower feed-related expenses (Yafetto et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2021). These innovative feed sources come with potential challenges, including limited nutrient bioavailability and the presence of anti-nutritional factors. Researchers are exploring novel approaches to overcome these challenges. For example, one innovative solution involves producing feed silage by fermenting various agro-industrial waste materials (Yafetto et al., 2023). Various agro-industrial by-products can be valorized, either locally or on a larger scale, depending on the specific substrate (Yang et al., 2021). Some agro-industrial by-products can be valorized using green technologies without microbial involvement. For instance, wine lees contain significant quantities of components such as polysaccharides (3.5 % to 4.8 %), proteins (approximately 14 % to 16 %), lipids (around 5 % to 6 %), polyphenols (ranging from 2 to 16 g/kg), and other organic substances (De Iseppi et al., 2020). Wine lees have a substantial protein content, low pH, high total nitrogen concentrations, and essential amino acids (tyrosine, valine, aminocaproic acid). This

Fig. 4. Sustainable development in cattle breeding - A holistic waste management perspective.

makes them a potentially nutritious feed source for ruminants. However, the presence of polyphenols in these proteins renders a significant portion of the fraction non-assimilable for animals (De Iseppi et al., 2020). Therefore, extracting polyphenols can enhance the nutritive value of these by-products while simultaneously providing valuable animal feed. These approaches are anticipated to see near-term adoption, playing a vital role in advancing the sustainability of the broader agro-industrial sector.

4.2. Potential applications and challenges of cattle/dairy wastes management

The design of integrated biorefinery systems embraces a holistic, circular economy approach that prioritizes the complete and efficient use of waste and by-product streams from dairy and livestock operations (Fig. 4). Rather than focusing on the production of a single end product, as illustrated in Fig. 4, these systems aim to generate multiple value-added outputs such as compost, biofertilizers, biogas, biomethane, and reclaimed water while simultaneously improving resource efficiency and minimizing environmental impact (Ankathi et al., 2024; Besediuk et al., 2024; FAO, 2018; Gama Pantoja et al., 2022; Kuo et al., 2024; Styles et al., 2018; Tampio et al., 2024; van den Oever et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). In this model, manure and wastewater from cattle farming undergo treatment processes like solid-liquid separation and anaerobic digestion, leading to the recovery of energy (in the form of biogas and biomethane), nutrients, and clean water for on-farm reuse. The digestate can further be used to enrich soils, closing the nutrient loop by supporting crop and feed production. Additionally, dairy by-products are valorized into high-value compounds, supporting various sectors including agriculture, energy, and households. This multifunctional, integrated strategy enhances the economic viability and environmental performance of biorefineries, supporting long-term sustainability in the agro-industrial sector. By contrast, composting remains a low-cost, low-tech option that is widely accessible but provides limited greenhouse gas reduction and modest economic returns. Anaerobic digestion, while requiring higher investment, delivers greater environmental benefits by producing renewable energy and nutrient-rich digestate (Hoyos-Sebá et al., 2024; van den Oever et al., 2021). Several LCAs indicate that anaerobic digestion can achieve 60–70 % reductions in emissions relative to raw manure storage, whereas composting achieves lower reductions but remains valuable as a low-tech, decentralized solution in regions lacking biogas infrastructure (de Azevedo et al., 2017; van den Oever et al., 2021). Thus, composting may be best suited for small-scale farms, while anaerobic digestion is more effective at larger scales when integrated into energy and fertilizer markets.

One of the most abundant and significant by-products of the dairy industry is whey (Besediuk et al., 2024). Cheese whey, a by-product of cheese production, is a readily available and cost-effective renewable resource. Although primarily composed of water, it contains approximately 50 % of the milk solids. The quantity of generated whey is directly proportional to cheese production and can also vary depending on the milk type, resulting in an approximate yield of 9 liters of whey per kilogram of produced cheese (Lappa et al., 2019). Within biorefinery systems, microbial bioprocesses have emerged as a promising strategy for converting cheese whey into novel, value-added products. Fermentation of whey significantly reduces its organic load, particularly lactose, offering a sustainable and economically viable method for minimizing its environmental impact (Schoina et al., 2020).

Similarly, cattle waste is a versatile and renewable biomass with strong potential for biofuel production. Integrated biorefinery approaches that utilize manure and related residues contribute to environmental protection by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient runoff, while also supporting the EU's goals for circular agriculture and a sustainable bioeconomy (Gallego et al., 2025). Converting this waste into biogas, bioethanol, and biodiesel reinforces circular

economy principles, mitigates environmental pollution, and enables renewable energy production. However, realizing this potential requires continued advancements in bioconversion technologies, supportive policies, and investment in necessary infrastructure (Hoyos-Sebá et al., 2024).

Traditionally, organic waste treatment has relied on single bioprocesses, such as composting or, more recently, anaerobic digestion. While composting is simple and cost-effective for solid waste, it is energy-intensive due to forced aeration. Moreover, the end product often faces market limitations, either from low prices or rejection by users due to quality issues, such as contamination with metals or plastics. Over the past two decades, anaerobic digestion has expanded in municipal and industrial waste management, driven largely by policy incentives. These support the conversion of biogas into electricity, heat, or biomethane, enabling its use as a renewable energy source beyond the production site.

In terms of economic feasibility, biomethane production costs in Europe have dropped to around 80€/MWh, well below the 2022 average TTF gas price of 134 €/MWh (EBA, 2022). This competitiveness makes anaerobic digestion a more attractive option than composting, which generates limited revenue streams tied mainly to compost sales and is vulnerable to fluctuating demand. The added value of biomethane as a locally produced alternative to fossil fuels also enhances energy security and creates rural employment opportunities. Raw biogas contains 40–45 % CO₂, which is typically released if not captured (Ding et al., 2025). Emerging CO₂ capture strategies integrated with anaerobic digestion such as post-combustion capture, biological conversion using microalgae, or catalytic upgrading to synthetic fuels can significantly improve environmental performance by preventing direct CO₂ release (Campello Gómez & Gutiérrez, 2025). While these technologies remain costly and are mostly limited to large-scale or pilot plants, they offer potential to transform anaerobic digestion into a near carbon-neutral system when combined with biomethane production (Esquivel-Patiño & Nápoles-Rivera, 2021). Coupling biomethane upgrading with CO₂ valorization is increasingly seen as a pathway to both greater carbon efficiency and economic diversification in livestock biorefineries (Campello Gómez & Gutiérrez, 2025; Esquivel-Patiño & Nápoles-Rivera, 2021).

Another key strategy in the circular economy is the use of digestate as an anaerobic digestion by-product as a replacement for synthetic fertilizers (Ding et al., 2025; Hoyos-Sebá et al., 2024). Integrating digestate into EU farming practices supports strategic objectives related to resource efficiency, soil health, and carbon farming. It helps reduce dependence on synthetic fertilizers, as outlined in the Farm to Fork Strategy, while also addressing nutrient balance and restoring soil organic matter, central goals of the EU Soil Strategy (Zilio et al., 2023). Beyond its fertilization value, digestate is a by-product of anaerobic digestion, which enables renewable energy generation from livestock waste. Although minor losses in nutrient content or organic matter may occur during the digestion process, research indicates that the environmental benefits far outweigh these drawbacks (Tampio et al., 2024). To fully optimize its impact, both the energy yield and the nutrient and carbon content of the digestate should be systematically assessed. This integrated approach enhances climate change mitigation, improves soil fertility, and contributes to carbon capture, aligning with the EU's broader environmental and climate policy goals.

Last but not least is the valorization of cattle farming wastewater. Addressing the water footprint of cattle farming requires a systems-based approach that combines water reuse with integrated nutrient and waste management strategies (Chatzimpiros & Barles, 2010; FAO, 2018). Water footprint can be categorized in tree basic dimensions (Fig. 5), while cattle breeding wastewater contributes directly to the Grey Water Footprint, as it involves pollutants that require treatment or dilution to avoid environmental harm (FAO, 2018). Understanding and reducing this footprint is essential for improving water sustainability and achieving SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation). With approximately

Fig. 5. Components of the water footprint contributing to total water use—**Blue**: global blue water resources; **Green**: global green water resources; **Grey**: volume of water required to assimilate pollutants.

56 billion cattle currently raised worldwide each year, a figure projected to potentially double by 2050, the water demand associated with meat and dairy production is expected to rise substantially (Blanco-Vieites et al., 2024). Beef production, in particular, is highly water-intensive, with estimates indicating that approximately 76.7 liters of water are required to produce just one kilogram of beef (Blanco-Vieites et al., 2024).

A significant portion of water used in cattle farming becomes wastewater containing high levels of organic matter, nutrients, and pathogens, which can lead to environmental hazards such as nutrient pollution and decline in biodiversity. However, with appropriate treatment such as anaerobic digestion, liquid-solid separation, and nutrient recovery this waste can serve as a renewable water source. Since manure and slurry are over 85 % water, recovered water can be reused for non-potable purposes like irrigation, cleaning, and cooling (Simamora et al., 2025). Innovations that also improve productivity and animal health, especially in dry climates, are more likely to be adopted, particularly when supported by government incentives. A structured adoption process moving from awareness to implementation further facilitates uptake. This approach reduces reliance on freshwater, supports circular economy goals, and strengthens water resilience in livestock systems.

Overall, integrated biorefinery approaches demonstrate strong potential to enhance both environmental and economic sustainability in the bovine and dairy sectors by converting manure, wastewater, and dairy by-products into renewable energy, reclaimed water, and nutrient-rich fertilizers (Fig. 4). Their effectiveness, however, depends on scale, infrastructure, and supportive policy frameworks. Composting remains a viable low-cost option for smaller farms, while anaerobic digestion with downstream biomethane production, digestate utilization, and emerging CO₂ valorization offers greater long-term benefits where investment capacity and market integration are in place, reinforcing the transition toward a circular and resilient livestock bioeconomy.

5. Sustainability challenges in the bovine sector: aligning science, policy, and practice

The bovine production sector faces growing scrutiny due to its significant environmental impacts, particularly in relation to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, water resource use, nutrient pollution, and land degradation. Although cattle farming is essential for global food supply and supports rural economies, it significantly contributes to climate change, ecosystem degradation, and the pollution of freshwater resources. Addressing these sustainability challenges requires not only technological innovation but also the alignment of scientific research with coherent and responsive policy frameworks.

Historically, agricultural policies in the European Union (EU) especially through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) prioritized food security and farmer income. Introduced in 1962 in the post-war context, CAP focused on boosting agricultural productivity. However, this production-centric approach unintentionally led to widespread environmental degradation. Although policy reforms in the 1990s began incorporating environmental objectives, their implementation has not kept pace with the accelerating ecological consequences of intensive

livestock systems (Parliament, 2017).

Today, the environmental challenges posed by bovine production are compounded by rising global demand. With approximately 56 billion cattle currently raised annually, and projections suggesting a potential doubling by 2050, the sector's water and carbon footprints are expected to grow substantially. Beef production, in particular, is highly water-intensive, with estimates indicating that 76.7 liters of water are needed to produce 1 kg of beef. A considerable portion of this becomes wastewater, containing high loads of nutrients, organic matter, and pathogens that can severely impact aquatic ecosystems through eutrophication and biodiversity loss.

In response, technological solutions such as anaerobic digestion, liquid-solid separation, and nutrient recovery systems offer promising pathways to transform cattle waste into renewable energy, fertilizers, and reusable water. These processes align with circular economy principles, reduce environmental burdens, and enhance resource efficiency. For example, manure and slurry comprising over 85 % water can be treated and reused for irrigation, barn cleaning, and cooling, particularly in water-scarce regions. However, the adoption of such innovations remains uneven, often hindered by high costs, limited infrastructure, and regulatory complexity (Cheli et al., 2013; Kareem et al., 2018; Olper et al., 2014). Furthermore, the bovine sector operates within a highly globalized supply chain, making it vulnerable to external shocks. Climate variability, geopolitical instability, and trade imbalances such as those observed in feed-exporting regions or through milk import patterns (e.g., China's reliance on New Zealand) can disrupt production and exacerbate environmental pressures. Despite some countries advancing regulatory responses (e.g., water protection in New Zealand), similar efforts are often lacking in lower-income feed-exporting nations, underlining the need for globally coordinated, environmentally focused trade policies (Cheli et al., 2013; Kareem et al., 2018).

In addition, consumer behavior and public awareness play a pivotal role in shaping the sustainability of bovine production. There remains a widespread lack of understanding of waste prevention, circular practices, and the environmental costs embedded in livestock products. To overcome these barriers, collaboration between researchers, policy-makers, farmers, and consumers is essential. Initiatives focused on education, stakeholder engagement, and transparent communication can help drive the adoption of sustainable practices and support informed consumption. Ultimately, tackling sustainability challenges in the bovine sector requires an integrated, science-driven policy approach that connects innovation with practical application. Strengthening the interface between science and policy, fostering cross-sectoral collaboration, and implementing regionally tailored solutions are key to reducing the ecological footprint of cattle farming while maintaining food system resilience (Kayikci et al., 2022). Only through such holistic strategies can the sector contribute meaningfully to climate goals, water stewardship, and sustainable development.

6. Conclusions, opportunities, and future prospects

The bovine production sector faces mounting sustainability challenges, particularly in managing its environmental impacts within the framework of evolving EU regulations. Complex policy landscapes, high greenhouse gas emissions, water and nutrient pollution, and global supply chain pressures necessitate a strategic rethinking of how waste is managed in cattle farming. Effective integration of scientific innovation into regulatory and practical frameworks remains critical to addressing these issues.

One of the most pressing needs is the establishment of stronger linkages between scientific research, policy development, and industry practice. Bridging this gap is essential for implementing robust, science-based strategies that reduce the ecological footprint of bovine production. This includes the wider adoption of advanced waste treatment technologies, resource recovery systems, and circular economy principles that transform cattle waste into renewable energy, fertilizers, and

water resources. For example, manure-based anaerobic digestion in Europe has been shown to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by up to 70 % compared with conventional storage while supplying renewable biogas to local grids (Hoyos-Sebá et al., 2024; van den Oever et al., 2021). Similarly, whey valorization in the dairy sector can recover 50 % of milk solids as high-value ingredients, improving both sustainability and profitability (Lappa et al., 2019).

Education and capacity-building across all levels, from policymakers to producers and consumers are equally important. Informing stakeholders about sustainable practices, resource efficiency, and zero-waste objectives can drive behavioral change and support the broader goals of the EU Green Deal, Farm to Fork Strategy, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Yet, practical implementation faces multiple barriers. High upfront investment costs and long payback periods discourage smaller farms from adopting biogas or nutrient recovery systems. Technology adoption is further hindered by fragmented infrastructure and the lack of localized processing facilities, which makes resource recovery economically unattractive in rural or livestock-dense areas. Regional differences exacerbate these challenges: wealthier member states tend to advance circular solutions more quickly, while less developed regions struggle with policy enforcement and technical support. Even when infrastructure exists, social acceptance and behavioral resistance from both farmers and consumers may slow the uptake of circular economy innovations.

Looking forward, the development and adoption of a sustainability-centered management model for natural ecosystems and renewable resources will be vital. This model must account for environmental, economic, and social dimensions to ensure that resource use today does not compromise the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Critical to success will be aligning incentives with realistic adoption pathways. For example, coupling CAP payments with verifiable reductions in methane emissions could directly reward farmers for sustainability outcomes. Similarly, integrating digital monitoring tools with regulatory frameworks may improve transparency but raises concerns over data ownership, farmer autonomy, and unequal access to technology. Addressing these trade-offs openly is essential for credibility and long-term resilience. By fostering cross-sectoral collaboration, enhancing innovation uptake, and reinforcing regulatory support, the EU has an opportunity to lead a transformative shift in the bovine sector one that promotes environmental stewardship, economic resilience, and food system sustainability across generations. However, without confronting economic, technological, and social barriers head-on, these strategies risk remaining aspirational rather than actionable. A critical next step is to systematically evaluate not only the benefits of circular solutions but also their feasibility, scalability, and fairness across regions and farming systems.

Despite the significant challenges outlined, the bovine sector also holds immense opportunities to become a driver of sustainability within the EU framework. Advances in biotechnology, digital farming, and waste valorization are opening new avenues for reducing emissions, closing nutrient loops, and generating renewable energy. If coupled with coherent policies, equitable financing mechanisms, and active engagement of stakeholders across the supply chain, these innovations have the potential to transform waste streams into valuable resources that sustain farmers' livelihoods while advancing Europe's climate neutrality goals. Underpinned by the EU's evolving policy frameworks and rising consumer awareness, the transition toward a circular and resilient bovine sector is not only feasible but also increasingly demonstrated through emerging waste valorization initiatives and sustainable farming practices. Finally, by embracing collaboration, innovation, and adaptive governance, the sector can shift from being perceived primarily as a sustainability challenge to becoming an integral part of Europe's solution for a greener future.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Antonia Terpou: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Olga Arvaniti:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Nikos Afratis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Theodore Zahariadis:** Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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